

REALIZATION OF THE PRAGMATIC OBSTACLE IN THE WORKS OF ERKIN A'ZAM

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Abstract: *This article discusses the pragmatic obstacle, its manifestations, the pragmatic factors that create it, the opinions of scientists about it, and the realization of the pragmatic obstacle in the works of Erkin A'zam, its place in the work of art, and its pragmatic function.*

Key words: *Pragmatic obstacle, pragmatic factor, pragmatic function, expressiveness, pragmatic meaning.*

The process of information exchange is created by the speaker and the listener. The effectiveness of the conversation depends on their mutual understanding. In the same way, the reader needs certain knowledge and pragmatic thinking to understand the idea that the author wants to express in a work of art, the content of the dialogue between the characters of the work. After all, in a work of art, the author always uses certain hidden image tools without directly expressing his thoughts and artistic image. In this article, we discuss one such tool, the pragmatic obstacle.

In the scientific literature, the obstacles that arise in the process of perceiving information in a foreign language culture are divided into four groups:

1. Lexical-semantic obstacle;
2. Communication and pragmatic obstacles;
3. Obstacles caused by ignorance of culture;
4. Frame fences [6].

Lexical-semantic obstacles are usually associated with concepts formed in a foreign culture. Ignorance of the national-cultural features and artifacts found in the texts serves as an obstacle to understanding. In this case, not understanding the meaning of archaisms and historical words, the content they express, is an obstacle to the complete perception of reality.

Communication and pragmatic obstacles appear due to a lack of knowledge of social norms. For example, a younger person should not greet an older person, and not be rude to someone older than him by raising his voice, and women should respect men, and not go to the toilet with bare feet. My grandfather saw him come out of the toilet barefoot and sent "Obba! Astag'firullo!" The next day, he left his chorpoya and brought a pair of kalish from the store in Guzar, etc.

Misunderstandings related to the cultural fund are mainly caused by the fact that many facts of material and spiritual culture that happened in a certain historical period have not been preserved. In particular, if the text contains the names of legendary

heroes, khans, saints, names of narrations about historical events, etc., the addressee or reader who has not heard about it before will not be able to understand the text to the required level.

Framing obstacles arise due to misunderstanding of expressions related to traditions and customs. Ignorance of such “unwritten laws”, which must always be taken into account when reading texts, creates obstacles. For example, in the works of Erkin A’zam, in the image of the mourning ceremony, the state of “sadr down” is described, which is not done everywhere. If the reader does not have enough knowledge about “sadr down”, he will not understand or misperceive the content of the text.

The difficulties that arise during the reading process related to the understanding and interpretation of artistic texts can be divided into language and cultural barriers. Below, we will try to shed more light on the pragmatic obstacle with the help of examples taken from the works of Erkin A’zam.

The concept of pragmatic obstacles is clearly visible mainly in the communicative relationship between the speaker and the listener, especially in the imagination of the participants of the speech, and the leveling of world and language knowledge is considered the basis of pragmatic obstacles. A pragmatic obstacle is information about the speaker’s inner spiritual world as one of the manifestations of speech ethics [2, 126].

In general, some actions and words of our brother Abusharof began to seem more understandable to me. First, he calls himself “extrasense” and not “extraseanse” for some reason - even if he doesn’t know that! Then, he brags a lot about who and how great he has treated. It’s okay, as if he had made a conspiracy in advance, in front of his patients, Hadeb invites me to be a judge: “This is the person who saw it with his own eyes, let them say it themselves”, “This is the person who knows”, that patient went like a horse, didn’t he?”.

In short, all the secrets of our “miracle” doctor became clear to me, and this oil was enough to stop the chirping of a bird in a restless heart (“Noise”).

In this text, the author seems to have made a mistake by using the word “extrasense” instead of “extraseanse” in the speech of the hero of the work, but in fact, the use of these two words interchangeably makes this image serve as a node for the unfolding of events related to his entire character and life. That is, the hero named Abusharof works as a psychic, and in exchange for treating the wife of the director of the film studio, he is promised a film about his work. Under the pretext of studying his work and writing a screenplay, Farkhod said that he is not truly anyone, but that he is a “miracle” doctor in the eyes of people, that he is completely ignorant of the science of medicine and psychics, and that he is playing the role of a doctor, even the name of his activity. shows by not being able to say it right. The author cites the following notes about Abusharof’s later life: “later, someone assumed that he was mentally ill and went to a madhouse. Who else knows!”.

G. Toirova states that “pragmatic obstacle is an obstacle to the proposition that needs to be stated, obscuring its content, a phenomenon related to the speaker’s thinking and pronunciation (pragmatic pomex)” [5, 36].

L.A. Kiseleva, a linguist, speaking about the pragmatic obstacle, emphasizes the existence of nonlinguistic and linguistic manifestations of the pragmatic obstacle. The linguistic obstacle itself is divided into two categories: 1. Obstacles related to the formation of expression. According to this, too fast and unusual pronunciation and unreadability of written speech make it difficult to understand the content of the text as a pragmatic obstacle. 2. Obstacles related to the form of expression. Pragmatic obstacles in this group are also classified: a) irregular pronunciation b) irregular word usage (use of words inconsistent with their meaning); d) improper use of grammatical forms and syntactic devices, which also creates a pragmatic obstacle [4, 136]; and e) abnormal use of a certain functional style, which is also distinguished as a linguistic sign that creates a pragmatic obstacle [2, 127].

Or maybe he didn't get treatment because he was left behind in adolescence and his bones hardened? As mentioned in the old medicine books, “Add red batila to one part yellow honey, mix it with a pinch of amila, a spoonful of maccai sano and tortoise bile, sprinkle a paisa of jackfruit seeds, Ceylon cinnamon and fennel on it, and then one diram If Abu Jahl eats the seed of a watermelon and boils its bulb in ten-year-old narcissus water and eats it until midnight...” he was not interested in events like that - whether it will be successful or not, his life will be spent worrying about it (“Pakana’s Lover’s Heart”).

In this passage, we can see that a pragmatic obstacle is revealed through the illogically constructed sentences.

It is understood that the pragmatic obstacle, on the one hand, has a negative effect on the effective flow of speech and makes communication difficult, on the other hand, it creates effectiveness as a stylistic tool in an artistic text [3, 100]. Pragmatic obstacles do not affect the content of information reflected in the text when they act as a methodological tool; in contrast, their emotional and expressive coloring increases. A skilled writer makes good use of such tools.

Erkin A’zam is able to increase the artistic-imagery and aesthetic impact of the language of his works from the pragmatic obstacle to express the characters’ speech and character traits in a unique way, in addition to create an image specific to his individual style, to draw portraits of heroes and as a knot we also saw that it was used.

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